

Infrared Spectra of Coumarins and Chalkones

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IR spectra of some coumarins and chalkones are described. The implications of the various assignments are also discussed.

Although spectroscopic methods are becoming increasingly important in elucidating the structure of naturally occurring organic compounds, little attention has been paid, however, to coumarins and chalkones. The present work has therefore been undertaken to gain more information about the spectroscopic characteristics of coumarins and chalkones (which are intermediates for the synthesis of flavones), which may lead to interesting generalisations on the structure-spectra correlation in the coumarin and chalkone groups of compounds. The following coumarins and chalkones were prepared by known methods:

I. Coumarins: (a) 4-methyl-7-hydroxycoumarin¹, (b) 4-methyl-6-hydroxycoumarin¹, (c) 4-methyl-6-carboxylic-7-hydroxycoumarin¹, (d) 4-methyl-7-methoxycoumarin, (e) 4-methyl-7-acetoxycoumarin², (f) 4-methyl-7-hydroxy-8-acetylcoumarin², (g) 4-hydroxycoumarin³, (h) 3-ethoxycarbonylcoumarin⁴, (i) 4-methyl- α -naphthacoumarin⁵, (j) 4-methyl-5,7-dihydroxycoumarin⁵.

II. Chalkones: (a) chalkone⁶, (b) 2-hydroxychalkone⁶, (c) 3'-nitrochalkone⁶, (d) 3-nitrochalkone⁶, (e) 2-hydroxy-3'-nitrochalkone⁶, (j) 4'-phenylchalkone⁶, (g) 4,4'-dimethoxychalkone⁷, (h) 4-methoxy-4'-ethoxychalkone⁷, (i) 2'-hydroxychalkone⁸, (j) 2'-methoxychalkone, (k) 2'-acetoxychalkone.

The coumarin (d) was prepared by methylation of the coumarin (a) by diazomethane. The chalkones (j) and (k) were prepared by methylation with diazomethane and acetylation of the chalkone (i), respectively.

1. Pechmann and Duisberg, *Ber.*, 1883, 16, 2119.
2. Russel and Fryo, "*Org. Synthesis*", Vol. 21, p. 22.
3. Shah *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1960, 25, 677.
4. Horning *et al.*, "*Org. Synthesis*", Vol. 28, p. 24.
5. Appel, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1031.
6. Jadav and Kulkarni, *Curr. Sci.*, 1951, 20, 42.
7. Rohrmann *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 66, 1856.
8. Mahal and Venkataraman, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 617.

The analytical data of the chalkones, not found in literature, will be published elsewhere.

The spectral measurements were made in a Perkin Elmer Model 21 Double Beam Infrared Spectrophotometer by taking the sample in a paraffin mull.

Coumarins

The infrared data of the coumarins are described in Table I. In coumarins, the multiple conjugation makes it quite difficult to attempt a specific assignment of the lactone carbonyl group and the double bonds. But certain characteristic features, however, need special mention.

Absorption around 5.8-6.0 μ region.—When there are free -OH groups in 5- or 7-position, no band is observed in 5.8-5.9 μ region where the lactonic carbonyl band is expected. The band appears on the other hand at 5.98 μ in the case of 7-hydroxy (No. 5) and 6.0 μ in the 5,7-dihydroxy (No. 3). When the hydroxy group is present in the 4-position (No. 2), the band expected for the lactonic carbonyl appears at 6.05 μ . In coumarins with -OH group at 6-position (No. 4), there is a band at 5.9 μ , which may be attributed to the lactonic carbonyl group. These results show that the effect of hydroxy group on the absorption in 5.8-6.0 μ region, which is characteristic of the lactonic carbonyl absorption, is maximum in the case of -OH in 4-position and this decreases in the sequence: -OH in 4-position > -OH in 5- and 7-positions > -OH in 7-position > -OH in 6-position.

When the -OH groups are methylated (No. 7) or acetylated (No. 8), the band appears at 5.8 μ . It is of sufficient interest to mention that in the case of 4-methyl-7-hydroxy-8-acetylcoumarin (No. 6), where there is possibility of chelation between the hydroxyl group and acetyl group, the band appears at 5.8 μ . Interaction of the hydroxyl group and the acetyl group and participation of the resulting resonance forms, as postulated in the case of *o*-hydroxyacetophenone, must have been responsible for the shift to shorter wave length.

Additional conjugation in the form of phenyl ring also pushes the band to higher wave length in the region around 5.84 μ . The relative influence of the hydroxy group in 4,5,6, and 7 positions is understandable because of the conjugation of the -OH groups in these positions with the carbonyl group. The effect of the ethoxycarbonyl group in 3-position in coumarin (No. 9) is significant because of the appreciable shift to shorter wave lengths around 5.68 μ .

The hydroxyl bands in 6-hydroxy- (No. 4), 7-hydroxy- (No. 5), and in 4-hydroxy- (No. 2) coumarins appear respectively at 3.08 μ , 2.95 μ , and 3.1 μ (very weak). There is no -OH band in the case of 5,7-dihydroxycoumarin (No. 3), most probably due to hydrogen bonding. It is significant that examination of the 2.85 μ to 4.0 μ (3500-2500 cm^{-1}) region of the spectrum in 4-methyl-7-hydroxy-8-acetylcoumarin (No. 6) does not show the presence of any band, characteristic of a hydroxy group. Similar behaviour was also observed in *o*-hydroxyanthraquinone⁹ and in *o*-hydroxyacetophenone¹⁰ and it was attributed to intramolecular hydrogen bonding.

9. Flett, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 1441.

10. Gardy, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1940, 8, 516.

TABLE II

Chalkones.

S. No.	Chalkone	6.0s	6.23s	6.36m	6.7π	6.9s	7.28w	7.66w	8.25m	9.68w	9.86m	10.14m	13.35s
1	Chalkone						7.9m	7.8w					14.57s
2	2'-Hydroxy-	6.1s	..	6.35s	6.75s	..	7.48s	7.9w	8.1w	9.71m	10.07w	10.26s	13.3s
								7.65s	8.32s			11.6m	13.55s
									8.7s			12.08w	
3	2'-Methoxy-	6.2s	..	6.35s	6.55s	..	7.45m	7.95m	8.08w	9.06w	..	10.73w	13.04m
					6.70s				8.4m	9.3w		11.42s	13.26m
									8.75s	9.67w			
4	2-Hydroxy-	6.1s	6.27s	6.33m	..	..	7.47m	7.73w	8.17m	9.8m	..	10.15m	13.36m
				6.4s					8.7m			11.66w	13.73m
												11.95w	
5	2-Hydroxy-3-nitro-	6.07s	6.27s	6.4s	6.55s	..	7.45s	7.7w	8.27w	..	..	10.2w	13.1w
												11.6w	13.27w
													13.73m
6	2'-Acetoxy-	5.7s	6.25s	6.36s	..	6.9s	7.54s	7.7m	8.3	8.95m	9.85m	10.04m	12.9m
		6.01s						7.8m	8.5 (dif.)	9.07m		10.97s	13.3s
		6.1s										12.13m	14.3s
7	4,4'-Dimethoxy-	6.05s	6.3s	6.37m	6.65w	7.00w	7.5m	7.7m	8.0s	9.0w	..	10.16m	12.31s
									8.26m	9.7w		11.85w	13.4w
									8.6s	9.87m		12.15s	
8	4-Methoxy-4'-ethoxy-	6.05m	6.3s	6.4m	6.07w	7.05m	..	7.78m	8.0s	9.0w	..	10.22w	12.25m
									8.35m*	9.5w		10.9w	12.5w
									8.56s	9.75m			
9	4'-Phenyl-	6.05m	6.3m	6.45w			..			9.7w		10.2w	13.35m
				6.65w								12.0w	
10	3'-Nitro-	6.05m	6.22s	6.55s			7.45s	7.65w	8.3m	9.25m	..	10.2w	13.0m
												11.7w	13.55m
11	3-Nitro-	6.05s	6.22s	6.35w			7.43s	7.8w	8.22m	9.3w	9.65m	10.25w	12.87m
				6.55s								11.03w	13.65s
												12.35w	14.2m

It is difficult to attempt any further correlation without further investigation, which is in progress.

Chalkones

The infrared data of the chalkones prepared are recorded in Table II. It is a well-known observation in infrared spectroscopy that conjugation of ethylenic double bonds or a carbonyl double bond causes a shift from its normal position to a longer wave length. Thus in acetone, the band for the unconjugated carbonyl group appears at 5.81μ (1718 cm^{-1}). If the carbonyl group is conjugated with one phenyl group, as in acetophenone, the frequency is decreased to 1687 cm^{-1} , the corresponding wave length being 5.94μ . Conjugation with two phenyl groups, as in benzophenone, shifts the wave length further to 6.05μ . This is because whenever there is increased opportunity for the contribution of the ionic resonance structure (A) to the carbonyl group (B),

a shift to higher wave length or lower frequency is observed.

Unsubstituted chalkone, i.e., benzylideneacetophenone, shows a carbonyl band at 1659 cm^{-1} (6.02μ), which is due to conjugation with phenyl group and an aliphatic double bond.

In the chalkones studied by us (unsubstituted in *ortho* positions), the carbonyl bands appear at the positions indicated in Table III and are within the region 6.0 - 6.05μ .

TABLE III

*No.	Chalkones.	Position of absorption band (in μ).
1	Chalkone	6.0 s
7	4,4'-Dimethoxy-	6.05 s
8	4-Methoxy-4'-ethoxy-	6.05 s
9	4'-Phenyl-	6.05 s
10	3'-Nitro-	6.05 s
11	3-Nitro-	6.05 s

The number refers to those in Table II.

Introduction of hydroxy group in 2'-or 2-position is expected to shift the carbonyl band to higher wave length. This expectation is also realised in the chalkones studied by us. The position of carbonyl bands of the chalkones prepared by us are shown in Table IV.

TABLE IV

*No.	Chalkones.	Position of absorption band (in μ).
2	2'-Hydroxy-	6.1
4	2-Hydroxy-	6.1
5	2-Hydroxy-3-nitro-	6.07

The number refers to those in Table II.

As expected, acetylation was found to cause the absorption band to return to the original position. Thus in the chalkones, prepared by us, the carbonyl band of 2'-hydroxychalkone appears at 6.1 μ , but 2'-acetoxychalkone exhibits its carbonyl band at 6.01 μ (No. 6, Table II).

The effect of a hydroxy group, *ortho* to keto group, was first noted in *o*-hydroxyacetophenone¹⁰ and this was attributed to hydrogen bonding between the hydroxy group and keto group. Rasmussen *et al.*¹¹, however, considered that the shift was due to a conjugated chelate system. Careful examination of the 2.85 μ to 4.0 μ (3500-2500 cm^{-1}) region of the spectrum of *o*-hydroxyacetophenone indicates the absence of any band characteristic of a hydroxy group. Similar behaviour was also observed in *o*-hydroxyanthraquinone⁹ and it was attributed to intramolecular hydrogen bonding. It is argued that conjugated chelation is responsible for the shift to shorter wave length. *o*-Methoxyacetophenone, where clearly neither hydrogen bonding nor chelation is possible, shows, however, a band at 1649 cm^{-1} (6.06 μ). It seems likely therefore that this shift to longer wave length is due to participation of the resonance forms such as (I) in hydroxy derivative and (II) in the case of the methoxy derivative. The increased stabilisation in (I) due to chelation plus the greater ability of the hydroxy group to donate electrons to the ring is responsible for the absorption in high wave-length region in (I) and (II). The capability of the acetoxy group to donate electrons is very meagre and this accounts for the acetoxy derivatives not markedly differing from unsubstituted acetophenone.

The influence of *o*-hydroxy, *o*-methoxy and *o*-acetoxy groups in the IR absorption pattern of chalkones has been observed by us to be the same as that in the case of acetophenone (Table V).

TABLE V

No.	Chalkone.	Position of carbonyl absorption band (in μ).
1	Chalkone	6.0
2	2'-Hydroxy-	6.1
6	2'-Acetoxy.	6.01
3	2'-Methoxy-	6.2

The number refers to those in Table II

It is significant that 2'-hydroxychalkone does not show the characteristic hydroxyl band and this must be due to intramolecular hydrogen bonding.

Examination of the IR data of the chalcones, described in Table II, reveals that the band due to the conjugated $-C=C-$ bond has been resolved in a few cases. There appears only a weak shoulder on either the carbonyl band or on the aromatic band around $6.3-6.6 \mu$, associated with the aromatic $-C=C-$ double bond. The two major $-C=C-$ frequencies in the $6-7 \mu$ region are well pronounced and occur from 6.3 to 6.4μ and from 6.7 to 6.9μ . For the purpose of structure assignment, the most useful portion of these infrared spectra are $7.6-7.8 \mu$ and $10.2-10.4 \mu$ regions where the $-CH-$ deformation frequencies, characteristic of *trans*-ethylenic bond, are found.

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